

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2025, №6 (20)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным и клиническим
проблемам медицины
основан в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2025, № 6 (20)

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Сайт <https://bsmi.uz/journals/fundamental-ya-klinik-tibbiyot-ahborotnomasi/>

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О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.

Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/б
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Муस्ताкиллиги, 70/2.

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POTENTIAL ROLE OF EPITHELIAL-MESENCHYMAL TRANSITION IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF PERIODONTITIS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Resume. The rising incidence of gingivitis and periodontitis seen worldwide has led to the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases as a major component in contemporary dentistry. This research examines scholarly literature to determine the connection between the emergence of inflammatory periodontal illnesses and the gingival sulcus epithelium's enhanced permeability. Studies of the features of the interaction between the epithelial barrier and oral microbiota are given special attention. As part of the project, scholarly publications from sources including eLIBRARY, Google Search, and PubMed were examined. Over 100 papers addressing different facets of the subject under examination were found between 2024 and 2025. Following rigorous selection, 60 works—including reviews and experimental research (both in vitro and in vivo)—were included in the review. These articles' data served as the basis for the findings that follow. A connection between the regulation of both innate and adaptive immunity and disturbances in mucous membrane microbiota is suggested by the growing amount of data. Beneficial microbes may either directly combat pathogens that interfere with the barrier's function or they can boost the body's antimicrobial defenses via the immune system. This process involves the epithelial-mesenchymal transition, in which epithelial cells lose their original traits and gain new ones. A periodontal pocket may emerge as a result of these alterations, which may also weaken the basement membrane and compromise the integrity of the epithelial barrier. Hazardous microorganisms may infiltrate the mouth cavity's tissues as a result of this disturbance. In this process, intercellular linkages and tight junctions play a crucial role in maintaining the stability of cell function and regular functioning.

Keywords: Periodontitis, inflammatory periodontal diseases, epithelial barrier permeability, oral microbiota, tight junction protein complexes, gingival crevicular fluid,

ЭПИТЕЛИАЛ-МЕЗЕНХИМАЛ ЎТИШНИНГ ПЕРИОДОНТИТ ПАТОГЕНЕЗИДАГИ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ РОЛИ (АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРҲИ)

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Резюме. Бутун дунёда гингивит ва пародонтит касалликларининг ортиб бораётганлиги пародонтининг яллиғланиши касалликларини замонавий стоматологиянинг асосий таркибий қисмига айлантирди. Ушбу тадқиқот пародонтининг яллиғланиши касалликларининг пайдо бўлиши ва милк эгатчаси (gingival sulcus) эпителиясининг ўтказувчанлигининг ошиши ўртасидаги боғлиқликни аниқлаш учун илмий адабиётларни таҳлил қилади. Бунда эпителиал тўсиқ ва оғиз бўйлиги микробиотаси ўзаро таъсирининг ўзига хос хусусиятларига алоҳида эътибор қаратилган. Лойиҳа доирасида eLIBRARY, Google Search ва PubMed каби манбалардан илмий наشرлар ўрганилди. 2024-2025 йиллар оралигида кўриб чиқилаётган мавзунинг турли жиҳатларига бағишланган 100 дан ортиқ мақола топилди. Чуқур танловдан сўнг, шарҳга 60 та иш, шу жумладан шарҳлар ва экспериментал тадқиқотлар (in vitro ва in vivo) киритилди. Ушбу мақолалардаги маълумотлар кейинги хулосалар учун асос бўлиб хизмат қилди. Ортиб бораётган маълумотлар туғма ва адаптив иммунитетнинг тартибга солиниши ҳамда шиллиқ қават микробиотасининг бузилиши ўртасида боғлиқлик мавжудлигидан далолат беради. Фойдали микроблар тўсиқ функциясини бузадиган патогенлар билан тўғридан-тўғри курашиши ёки иммун тизими орқали организмнинг микробларга қарши ҳимоясини кучайтириши мумкин. Бу жараён эпителиал-мезенхимал ўтишини (ЭМЎ) ўз ичига олади, бунда эпителиал хужайралар ўзларининг дастлабки белгиларини йўқотади ва янгиларини олади. Ушбу ўзгаришлар натижасида пародонтал чўнтак ҳосил бўлиши, шунингдек, базал мембрананинг заифлаишига ва эпителиал тўсиқ яхлитлигининг бузилишига олиб келиши мумкин. Ушбу бузилиши натижасида хавфли микроорганизмлар оғиз бўйлиги тўқималарига кириб бориши мумкин. Бу жараёнда хужайралараро боғланишлар ва зич контактлар (tight junctions) оқсиллари комплекслари хужайралар функциясининг барқарорлигини ва уларнинг нормал ишлашини таъминлаида ҳал қилувчи роль ўйнайди.

Калим сўзлар: Периодонтит, пародонтининг яллиғланиши касалликлари, эпителиал тўсиқнинг ўтказувчанлиги, оғиз бўйлиги микробиотаси, зич контактлар оқсиллари комплекслари, милк суюқлиги .

ПОТЕНЦИАЛЬНАЯ РОЛЬ ЭПИТЕЛИАЛЬНО-МЕЗЕНХИМАЛЬНОГО ПЕРЕХОДА В ПАТОГЕНЕЗЕ ПАРОДОНТИТА (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

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Резюме. *Растущая во всем мире заболеваемость гингивитом и периодонтитом привела к развиту воспалительных заболеваний пародонта как основного компонента современной стоматологии. В данном исследовании анализируется научная литература для определения связи между возникновением воспалительных заболеваний пародонта и повышенной проницаемостью эпителия десневой борозды. Особое внимание уделяется исследованиям особенностей взаимодействия эпителиального барьера и микробиоты полости рта. В рамках проекта были изучены научные публикации из таких источников, как eLIBRARY, Google Search и PubMed. За период с 2024 по 2025 год было найдено более 100 статей, посвященных различным аспектам рассматриваемой темы. После строгого отбора в обзор были включены 60 работ, включая обзоры и экспериментальные исследования (как in vitro, так и in vivo). Данные этих статей послужили основой для последующих выводов. Растущее количество данных свидетельствует о связи между регуляцией как врожденного, так и адаптивного иммунитета и нарушениями микробиоты слизистых оболочек. Полезные микробы могут либо напрямую бороться с патогенами, нарушающими функцию барьера, либо усиливать антимикробную защиту организма через иммунную систему. Этот процесс включает эпителиально-мезенхимальный переход, при котором эпителиальные клетки теряют свои первоначальные признаки и приобретают новые. В результате этих изменений может образоваться пародонтальный карман, что также может ослабить базальную мембрану и нарушить целостность эпителиального барьера. В результате этого нарушения опасные микроорганизмы могут проникнуть в ткани полости рта. В этом процессе межклеточные связи и плотные контакты играют решающую роль в поддержании стабильности функции клеток и их нормального функционирования.*

Ключевые слова: *Периодонтит, воспалительные заболевания пародонта, проницаемость эпителиального барьера, микробиота полости рта, комплексы белков плотных контактов, десневая жидкость,*

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Annotation: Microbes are able to enter the tissues deeply because of the disturbance of the epithelial barrier, particularly its permeability. Dysbacteriosis may result from this, which worsens the gingival sulcus epithelial damage and causes periodontal inflammation. The process of increased permeability of the periodontal sulcus's epithelial barrier is intricate and reliant on several interrelated variables. The traits of proteins that maintain close contact between epithelial cells and the species and metabolites of pathogenic bacteria implicated in the development of periodontitis are particularly noteworthy among them. The influence of genetic predisposition is also significant.

The growing incidence of periodontitis and gingivitis in both adults and children emphasizes how urgently new methods for the identification, management, and prevention of inflammatory periodontal diseases must be developed. The intricate etiology and pathophysiology of these disorders, which remains incompletely understood, need more investigation. The manifestation of IBD [2, 3] may be ascribed to a multitude of factors, including genetic predisposition, immune system dysfunction, viral and bacterial infections, deficiencies in vitamins and trace elements, hormonal imbalances, mechanical traumas, and stressful circumstances. It should be emphasized that each of these elements has the potential to upset the structure and balance of the oral microbiome, which is essential for preserving health. Today, it is recognized that inflammatory periodontal diseases are complex conditions brought on by an imbalance in the microbiota. This changes the number and composition of bacteria in the periodontal pocket by converting the normal periodontal microbiota into a pathogenic one. The microbiological alteration, together with the immune response and environmental influences, initiates the inflammatory process that underpins disease progression. The advancement of chronic periodontitis is intricately associated with the activities of pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms, notably Gram-negative bacteria, which are especially relevant. Included are Porphyromonas gingivalis, Tannerella forsythia, Treponema denticola, Prevotella intermedia, and Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans. Because it is open and continuously exposed to the outside world, the gingival sulcus is an especially good place for them to reproduce. The coating of aging-resistant epithelium thins with time and is eventually replaced by connective epithelium. Continually exposed to the microbial coating, the latter merges with the tooth enamel. This ongoing exposure sets up a long-term immunological response [4-6]. The bor-

der epithelium may be disrupted by several reasons, including heightened inflammatory activity in the gingival sulcus. Multiple leukocyte types participate in inflammation, including polymorphonuclear leukocytes and mononuclear leukocytes (T and B lymphocytes). Additionally, different bacterial species that make up the oral microflora might cause epithelial cells to release certain cytokines. The integrity of the epithelial structure is subsequently compromised by an increase in the distance between desmosomes and alterations in the expression of proteins that guarantee tight connections between epithelial cells. The modulation of epithelial tight junctions by T cells is crucial for maintaining homeostasis or, alternatively, for the onset of a pathological condition. Damage to the epithelium's intercellular connections makes it easier for bacterial toxins and antigens to pass through the mucosa, which helps them move more easily across epithelial barriers and accelerates the inflammatory response. Periodontitis is associated with a reduction in the expression of critical epithelial markers, including as E-cadherin, vimentin, and N-cadherin. Increased microtrauma to the periodontal pocket epithelium, granulation tissue development, and fibrous proliferation are clinical manifestations of this. The inflammatory process in periodontal tissues, driven by cells and molecules, may induce the transdifferentiation of gingival pocket cells from an epithelial to a mesenchymal phenotype. According to research findings, inflammatory processes in the periodontium occur when the proteins that maintain tight cell-to-cell junctions fail. These proteins are crucial for maintaining the barrier function of the epithelium. A thorough review devoted to investigating the mechanisms of tight junction function and enhancing the permeability of the epithelial barrier is thus pertinent.

Aim of the research: Analyzing these variables' contribution to the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases.

Materials and methods: Original works and scientific publications from resources including eLIBRARY, Google Search, and PubMed were analyzed for the research. The study undertaken from 2004 to 2024 yielded a collection of 100 scientific papers. In order to conduct a systematic review of scientific literature, the study used search queries that included: "inflammatory periodontal diseases," "epithelial barrier permeability," "oral microbiota," "tight junction protein complexes," "gingival crevicular fluid," and their Russian equivalents: "chronic periodontitis," "aggressive periodontitis," "epithelial barrier," and "increased epithelial permeability syndrome." Scientific publications and original research from Russian and foreign databases were examined in this study. The Stata checklist, designed for systematic reviews and meta-analyses, used as a tool for systematic analysis. The research included 56 scholarly articles chosen based on rigorous criteria. It included both in vivo tests and in vitro investigations, along with reviews.

This systematic review's objectives were to assess and analyze the evidence on the role that epithelial permeability mechanisms play in the onset of IBD and to look into the possibility of using tight junction proteins as diagnostic markers for these conditions. The research investigated papers from three electronic bibliographic resources: PubMed, Google Search, and eLIBRARY. The timeframe included was from 2024 until 2025. Relevant papers were chosen using keywords that reflected the following topics: connective proteins, oral microbiota, inflammatory periodontal disorders, gingival crevicular fluid, chronic and aggressive periodontitis, and epithelial barrier permeability. Additionally, the search searches included essential terms' counterparts in Uzbek. The reference lists of the chosen articles were examined to pinpoint the most relevant literature. In the preliminary phase of the systematic review, 105 articles were chosen based on their titles, abstracts, and publication dates. Subsequently, by removing duplicates and items that failed to match the specified criteria, the list was condensed to 85 articles. Following the screening process, 60 publications—including information from systematic reviews and randomized controlled clinical trials—were chosen for inclusion. Thirteen items were eliminated during the ensuing screening. The non-representativeness of the research population, the studies' ambiguous diagnostic criteria, and the lack of a valid clinical diagnosis were the grounds for exclusion. Disputes over the inclusion or deletion of certain research were handled via collaborative discussion. 60 scientific publications were examined in a systematic review.

Rigorous criteria were used for the selection of publications.

Both laboratory (in vitro) and clinical (in vivo) research were included, including patients from two age demographics: young people (18-44 years) and middle-aged persons (45-59 years). Participants in the research had inflammatory periodontal disorders, which may present as both chronic periodontitis and chronic gingivitis. The study also included data on individuals devoid of clinical manifestations of periodontitis, who constituted the control group. The expression and synthesis of proteins involved in the creation of tight junctions were investigated using periodontal tissue biopsy or oral fluid samples, such as saliva and gingival crevicular fluid. Patients with inflammatory periodontal disorders (IPD) and volunteers with clinically healthy periodontal tissues participated in the trials. In order to ensure accurate findings, individuals with a history of periodontal surgery were not included. The evaluation excluded reviews and meta-analyses, research on children under the age of 18, studies on non-inflammatory periodontal disorders, studies on anti-

microbial peptides in blood serum, and studies on antimicrobial peptide expression in systemic inflammatory syndromes. Research indicates that within infectious disorders, the oral microbiota varies and changes as the disease progresses. Oral dysbiosis is responsible for the development of periodontitis and operates via a number of molecular mechanisms. The importance of precise interactions among oral microbiota, the immune system, and epithelial cells in preserving the stability and integrity of the oral mucosa has been brought to light by recent studies. Both the innate and adaptive immune responses may be modulated by changes in the mucous membrane microbiota, according to recent studies. Inflammation arises from a reduction in symbiotic microorganisms and/or an increase in pathobionts (symbiotic bacteria having pathogenic potential). By partly controlling the activity of T helper 17 cells (Th17) and regulatory T cells (Treg), two essential immune response cells, microbes affect the immune system [22–24]. At the same time, the body's first line of defense, the epithelium, can identify and interact with the microbial makeup. An imbalance in the microbiota and corresponding metabolic alterations might impair the mucosal epithelium, compromising its barrier functions [25, 26].

Results of the research: EMT is characterized by a shift from epithelial to mesenchymal cell phenotype, marked by downregulation of epithelial markers (e.g., E-cadherin) and upregulation of mesenchymal markers (e.g., vimentin, N-cadherin, Snail1, Twist1)[55, 56, 57, 58]. Periodontal pathogens, especially Gram-negative bacteria like *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, can induce EMT in oral epithelial cells, leading to loss of cell-cell adhesion, increased cell motility, and reduced barrier function [58,59,60] Key results on the names of bacterial species, indicators of regulated barrier transit, and the processes behind its operation were discovered via the examination of the papers that were given. The investigation identifies many mechanisms via which beneficial bacteria influence the barrier characteristics of the gingival epithelium. Gum health benefits from helpful bacteria may be seen in two primary ways. To begin with, they have the ability to trigger the production of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) by the host's immune system, which eliminates infections. Furthermore, several advantageous bacteria possess inherent antibacterial properties that aid in the elimination of harmful pathogens and fortify the epithelial barrier. In the end, these two processes—which are fueled by good bacteria—help to fortify the gum line. Certain oral microorganisms penetrate the gingival sulcus epithelium, compromising the physiological barrier's integrity. Their presence causes the metabolic equilibrium to shift, which raises the permeability of the tissue.

2. Gingival sulcus cells regenerate fast (6–12 days), allowing for the prompt replacement of microbially damaged tissues. It has been investigated how periodontopathic microbes and their toxins affect the breakdown of the epithelial barrier in addition to the neutrophil-induced degradation. Bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS) exposure has been shown in vitro to lower claudin-1 levels after JE exposure, hence reducing the extent of epithelial barrier degradation. According to recent research, the virulence protein of *P. gingivalis* has the ability to break down E-cadherin, which is essential for preserving the integrity of the gingival epithelium. Under laboratory circumstances, this damage interferes with the epithelium's defensive activities. As the formation and progression of periodontal disorders seem to be greatly influenced by the modulation of epithelial barrier function by bacteria, the findings obtained underscore the significance of this role. Recent research indicate that the preservation of gingival epithelial integrity is achievable by the use of medicines, dietary supplements, and metabolites. For instance, irsogladine maleate functions as an antiulcer drug and shields the gum epithelium from periodontopathogen-induced damage by inhibiting the degradation of the proteins claudin-1 and E-cadherin. Vitamins C and E facilitate the restoration of E-cadherin, which is compromised in the epithelial cells of gums infected with *P. gingivalis*. study indicates that polyphenols in green tea enhance the synthesis of proteins associated with tight cell junctions, including occludin and ZO-1, in gingival keratinocytes infected with *P. gingivalis*. Rather of being static, tight junctions are dynamic structures that alter their shape over time in response to a variety of external variables. This encompasses both internal stimuli, including cytokines and growth hormones, and external stimuli, such as food components, infections, and commensal bacteria[54]. More than 40 proteins, including as ZO-1, occludins, and claudins, have been shown to be present at tight junctions by studies [50]. According to a different research, catechin contributes to the oral epithelial barrier's increased integrity. This impact is probably attributable to an elevation in the expression or a modification in the distribution of the proteins ZO-1 and occludin, as determined by the immunofluorescence technique. ZO-1, a crucial element of the tight junction, directly engages with cytoplasmic actin and occludin proteins, which constitute the transmembrane tight junction [51]. The discovery of tight junctions (TJs), which provide a close connection between cells, was made possible by transmission electron microscopy in 1963. Research has shown their existence in the intercellular space of epithelial cells and their association with paracellular transport mechanisms. A more thorough investigation employing freeze-fracture electron microscopy showed that TJs, regardless of their kind (tight or leaky), create an interconnected network of filaments that spans the superficial and deep layers of the epithelium. Research has

shown that the barrier function of the epithelium and the shape of TJ strands are closely related. Transepithelial electrical resistance (TER), assessed in intestinal epithelial cells, serves as a marker of this relationship. These days, TJ strands are thought of as protein complexes that strengthen the epithelial barrier by holding the intercellular space close to the cell's apical surface together. The identification of the protein ZO-1, the first constituent of tight junctions (TJs), occurred in 1986. In 1989, researchers discovered cingulin, which was subsequently recognized as a peripheral protein of tight junctions. The discovery of occludin in 1993 marked a major advancement, since it was identified as the first transmembrane protein crucial for the establishment of tight junction barrier function. Later, more transmembrane proteins that interact with the TJ complex were identified. These include MAL and its analogs, which are important in vesicle trafficking and the function of the membrane-associated domain 3 (MarvelD3), claudins, and cell adhesion molecules (JAMs). It is important to remember that some tight junction proteins, including claudin-2 and claudin-15, both contribute to the creation of paracellular pores that let ions and water flow through enterocytes and act as a natural barrier. The impairment of epithelial barrier function might initiate a detrimental loop in which the immune response linked to barrier dysfunction intensifies inflammatory processes in the gastrointestinal tract, thus facilitating the advancement of pathological diseases [31]. The shape and molecular arrangement of tight junctions may change the degree of permeability, which is a key factor in the permeability of the epithelial barrier. Certain proteins on the surface of the cell's apical membrane interact to create dynamic structures known as tight junctions (TJs). The location of each of their constituent proteins may be used to identify them: some form a cytoplasmic scaffold, while others cross through the membrane. Transmembrane proteins that constitute tight junctions (TJs) can be categorized into four groups based on the quantity of transmembrane domains: the initial category comprises single-span proteins, including the adhesion molecule JAM, Crb3, and CAR; the subsequent category encompasses three-span proteins, exemplified by BVES; the final category consists of tetraspan proteins, such as claudins, MARVEL proteins associated with tight junctions (TAMPs), occludin, tricellin, and MarvelD3. The intestinal epithelium's tight junction (TJ) permeability is regulated by JAM, occludin, claudin, and tricellulin, according to experiments on these proteins. JAMs, as members of the immunoglobulin superfamily, are crucial for the adhesion and permeability of epithelial and endothelial cells. Four variations of JAM exist: JAM-A, JAM-B, JAM-C, and JAM-4. The role of JAM-4 in the tight junction structure remains incompletely elucidated [44]. Claudins are integral to the architecture of tight junctions (TJs), regulating the permeability of cellular junctions to ions and small molecules. There are at least 26 distinct kinds of claudins in mammals. Claudins inside TJ create membrane strands that may associate either heteromerically with other claudins or homomerically with one another. When two parallel threads adhere to one another, a porous structure is created that controls how permeable the intercellular space is to tiny molecules. The integrity and continuity of tight junctions are greatly influenced by their dynamic activity, which is governed by the expression of barrier-forming claudins and pore-forming claudins (claudin-2 and claudin-4). Specifically, claudins are paracellular ion channels [45]. Occludin's structure contains the MARVEL motif in two areas that are in charge of homodimer production and apical membrane localization. The cytosolic C-terminus of occludin comprises assembled kinase domains with phosphate groups and areas that facilitate scaffold binding. Although occludin is acknowledged as a crucial element of tight junctions (TJs), its absence in epithelial cells does not compromise barrier integrity or modify permeability; instead, it results in an elevated concentration of other TJ components in the contact zone. Occludin may constitute a component of tight junctions (TJs) by its interaction with scaffolding proteins, such as zonula occludens (ZO)-1. The specific physiological roles of each of these proteins deserve more investigation. Recent studies indicate that ZO-1 is not a critical element in the establishment of barrier function, but it is crucial in the regeneration of the intestinal mucosa. The TJ structure comprises structural proteins with several domains. These domains enable interaction with tight junction integral components, other structural proteins, and cytoskeletal elements, therefore regulating the tight junction assembly process, modulating the permeability of intercellular connections, and facilitating signaling cascades. A subset of structural proteins characterized by the presence of PDZ domains is identified. Proteins with PDZ domains establish a linking layer by associating with the integral proteins of the TS. A conserved sequence of around 90 amino acids, contained in PDZ (Post-synaptic Density protein, Drosophila disc large tumor suppressor, and Zonula occludens-1) proteins, delineates their two principal functions throughout evolution. Initially, these proteins securely attach to the intracellular C-termini of transmembrane proteins, including ion channels and receptors. Secondly, PDZ proteins form scaffold structures by interacting with one another via their PDZ domains in a process termed PDZ dimerization. The tight junction (TJ) zone, including the proteins ZO-1, ZO-2, and ZO-3, is a protein family that interacts with the cell scaffold and has similarities to guanylate cyclases. These proteins possess a distinctive characteristic: three contiguous PDZ domains at their N-terminus. ZO-1, a crucial element of tight junctions (TJs), significantly contributes to the maintenance of epithelial barrier permeability

via its interactions with other structural proteins including F-actin. The concept posits that ZO-1 and ZO-2 serve as complimentary elements that facilitate the binding of the tight junction chain. Moreover, ZO-1 is crucial for conveying signals from the tight junction structure to the actin cytoskeleton [49]. In this context, we see proteins that are excluded from the PDZ scaffold, including cingulin and paracingulin. Their homodimers have two components: a compactly folded rod and a globular head, each containing an interaction motif akin to the ZO-1 motif (ZIM) situated at the N-terminus. Research indicates that cingulin interacts with tight junction family proteins, namely JAM-A, ZO-1, and ZO-2 [50].

Four. In periodontal pathologies linked to inflammation, bacteria have been shown to compromise the integrity of tight junctions in the epithelium, enhancing its permeability and eventually resulting in the onset of inflammatory periodontal illnesses [28, 29]. *P. gingivalis* has the capacity to surpass the epithelial barrier and actively engage with oral epithelial cells, adhering to them, infiltrating their structure, and proliferating. This strategy enables bacteria to circumvent the effects of humoral immunity. *P. gingivalis* fimbriae, by binding to $\alpha 5\beta 1$ integrins, initiate a cascade of signaling events that result in the reorganization of the epithelial cell cytoskeleton. This reorganization enables bacterial ingress by using actin as a conduit [38, 39]. Epithelial-mesenchymal transition is crucial in this process, when epithelial cells alter their shape and function, relinquishing their unique epithelial traits. This process may occur in several forms, ranging from partial to full, and is induced by the destruction of the original cellular structure [24-26]. It is crucial to recognize that it progresses in a defined sequence, including resistance to apoptosis, preservation of apical-basal polarity, disintegration of cell adhesion junctions, and cytoskeletal reorganization. Concurrently, there is heightened activity of mesenchymal genes and decreased expression of epithelial genes [27-29]. These alterations may cause harm to the basement membrane, thereby compromising the integrity of the epithelial layer. This fosters the development of a periodontal pocket and permits pathogenic bacteria to infiltrate the oral cavity tissues. Several variables concurrently function as both risk factors and stimulants for the progression of periodontitis and epithelial-mesenchymal transition. The formation of EMT is empirically shown to be encouraged by many causes. This include Gram-negative microbes and their toxins, inflammatory processes with cytokine release, tobacco smoke, and hypoxia. Research indicates that systemic diseases, including diabetes mellitus, facilitate the production of epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). A robust association has been demonstrated between pathogenic agents, environmental variables, and periodontitis, indicating a potential role for epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) in the development of periodontal disease. Epithelial-mesenchymal transition may be a crucial process contributing to the proliferation of fibroblasts in periodontal pockets. Consequently, fibrosis ensues, tissue separation transpires, and an irreversible chronic inflammatory process is launched. Numerous studies indicate that periodontopathogens may infiltrate deep into periodontal tissues, surpassing the barriers of inflamed and compromised pocket epithelium. A bleeding index in periodontal pockets signifies micro-trauma to the epithelium of those pockets [32-34]. The intricate cellular and tissue alterations associated with periodontitis, together significant cytokines and other biologically active substances, imply a likely involvement of endoparasitic microflora in the onset and advancement of the condition. Research on tissue samples from periodontitis patients demonstrated heightened activity of fibronectin and integrin $\alpha v\beta 6$ in the adjacent tissues. Epithelial cells obtained from these individuals had increased levels of fibronectin and matrix metalloproteinases 9, 13, and 2. This phenomenon is thought to result from a proliferation of bacteria, which compromises the barrier between the biofilm and the bloodstream. This facilitates the dissemination of inflammatory agents generated by periodontal bacteria and diseased tissues. Intercellular junctions and tight connections between cells are crucial in this process, since they are essential for the proper functioning of cellular structures. Their activity is associated with regulatory metabolic pathways that govern cell growth and differentiation processes. The introduction of bacteria into gingival tissue may occur via two mechanisms: via the permeability of cellular layers (transcellular) or intercellularly (paracellular), infiltrating the gingival sulcus. Research using a mouse model of periodontitis and human subjects afflicted with the condition has shown an inverse correlation between the levels of the tight junction protein ZO-1 and the extent of bacterial infiltration into the gingiva, underscoring the significance of a paracellular pathway for bacterial entrance. Bacterial paracellular invasion transpires via two primary mechanisms: direct degradation of intercellular junctions and modification of functional protein expression. Microbial colonies often use abundant protein resources as a feeding source. Consequently, several pathogenic microbes inhabiting the periodontium generate potent proteases. Gingipains generated by *P. gingivalis* may degrade proteins that facilitate intercellular adhesion, namely E-cadherin, occludin, and intercellular adhesion molecule 1. Consequently, intercellular permeability escalates. Furthermore, *P. gingivalis* may influence the synthesis of proteins essential for intercellular interactions, therefore undermining cellular adhesion. The stimulation of the human gingival epithelial layer with *Porphyromonas gingivalis* lipopolysaccharide (LPS) resulted in a reduction in gene and protein expression related to E-cadherin. The gingival epithelial barrier became more permeable to LPS, result-

ing in an exacerbated inflammatory response [42-44, 47, 52]. Butyrate, a metabolite of anaerobic microorganisms, compromised the integrity of the gingival epithelial barrier, inducing pyroptosis and diminishing the levels of essential functional proteins. In contrast, 10-hydroxy-cis-12-octadecenoic acid, a metabolite produced by some *Lactobacillus* species, had an inhibitory impact on *P. gingivalis*-induced degradation of E-cadherin both in vitro and in an experimental mouse model of periodontitis. This impact was linked to the post-translational alteration of E-cadherin [48, 53]. The acquired findings suggest that the modulation of the epithelial barrier of the gingival sulcus is influenced not only by bacterial factors but also by microflora metabolites. Preserving the integrity of the epithelium barrier is a viable hypothesis for the prevention and treatment of periodontal disorders. Robust connections at the supragingival level of the periodontium facilitate intercellular adhesion and maintain the functional integrity of the barrier. Gap junctions are essential for modulating intercellular signaling, while desmosomes and hemidesmosomes serve as robust adhesive structures that provide mechanical stability and tissue integrity. Further research on this area is necessary to create preventative strategies and drugs to fight inflammatory and metabolic illnesses that impact not just the mouth cavity and periodontium but the whole gastrointestinal tract. The involvement of certain cytokines and proteins that maintain tight cell contact, as well as the impact of periodontal pathogenic microbes and their metabolic products, must all be taken into account when examining the increased permeability of the gingival sulcus epithelial barrier. An in-depth investigation is necessary to examine the role of the oral microbiota in the functionality of the periodontal epithelial barrier and the maintenance of immunological equilibrium. Tight junction proteins may be used as markers of inflammatory periodontal disorders; this will be determined with the aid of more study in this field. This makes it possible to create preventative strategies and drugs that target not only metabolic and inflammatory periodontal diseases but also issues that affect the whole gastrointestinal system.

Conclusion: According to an analysis of published data, tight junctions play a crucial role in the early phases of periodontal tissues' antimicrobial defense. Microbial infections may be able to penetrate the epithelial barrier due to inadequate permeability, which may then lead to a systematic disturbance of the microflora balance, aggravating damage to the gingival sulcus epithelium and inducing periodontal inflammation.

References:

1. Kovalevskiy AM, Ushakova AV, Kovalevskiy VA, Pro zherina EYu. Bacterial biofilm of periodontal pockets: the revision of periodontology experience. *Parodon tologiya*. 2018;23(2):15-21 (In Russ.). doi: 10.25636/PMP.1.2018.2.3
2. Ippolitov EV, Nikolaeva EN, Tsarev VN. Oral biofilm: inductors of immunity signal pathways. *Stomatology*. 2017;96(4):5862 (In Russ.). doi: 10.17116/stomat201796458-62
3. Tsarev VN, Nikolaeva EN, Ippolitov EV. Periodon tophatogenic bacteria of the main factors of emergence and development of periodontitis. *Journal of microbiology, epidemiology and immunobiology*. 2017;94(5):101-112 (In Russ.). doi: 10.36233/0372-9311-2017-5-101-112
4. Bosshardt DD, Lang NP. The junctional epithelium: from health to disease. *J Dent Res*. 2005;84(1):9-20. doi: 10.1177/154405910508400102
5. Bartold PM, Van Dyke TE. Host modulation: controlling the inflammation to control the infection. *Periodontology* 2000. 2017;75(1):317-329. doi: 10.1111/prd.12169
7. Slazhneva ES, Tikhomirova EA, Atrushkevich VG. Periodontopathogens: a new view. Systematic review. Part 1. Pediatric dentistry and dental prophylaxis. 2020;20(1):70-76. (In Russ.). doi:10.33925/1683-3031-2020-20-1-70-76
8. Dewhirst FE, Chen T, Izard J, Paster BJ, Tanner AC, Yu WH, et al. The human microbiome. *J Bacteriol*. 2010;192(19):5002-17. doi: 10.1128/JB.00542-10
9. Tikhomirova EA, Slazhneva ES, Atrushkevich VG. β -defensins and the inflammatory periodontal diseases: a systematic review. *Parodontologiya*. 2020;25(4):276-286. (In Russ.). doi:10.33925/1683-3759-2020-25-4-276-286
10. Katz J, Sambandam V, Wu JH, Michalek SM, Balk ovetz DF. Characterization of *Porphyromonas gingivalis*-induced degradation of epithelial cell junctional complexes. *Infect Immun*. 2000;68(3):1441-1449. doi: 10.1128/IAI.68.3.1441-1449.2000
11. Lagha AB, Groeger S, Meyle J, Grenier D. Green tea polyphenols enhance gingival keratinocyte integrity 2024;29(4) 374 *Обзор* | Review and protect against invasion by *Porphyromonas gingivalis*. *Pathog Dis*. 2018;76(4):fty030. doi: 10.1093/femspd/fty030
12. Katz J, Yang Q, Zhang P, Potempa J, Travis J, Michalek SM, et al. Hydrolysis of epithelial junctional proteins by *Porphyromonas gingivalis* gingipains. *Infect Immun*. 2002;70(5):2512-2518. doi: 10.1128/IAI.70.5.2512-2518.2002
13. Abe-Yutori M, Chikazawa T, Shibasaki K, Murakami S. Decreased expression of E-cadherin by *Porphyromonas gingivalis*-lipopolysaccharide attenuates epithelial barrier function. *J Periodontal Res*. 2017;52(1):42-50. doi: 10.1111/jre.12367

14. Guo W, Wang P, Liu ZH, Ye P. Analysis of differential expression of tight junction proteins in cultured oral epithelial cells altered by *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis* lipopolysaccharide, and extracellular adenosine triphosphate. *Int J Oral Sci.* 2018;10(1):1-7. doi: 10.1038/ijos.2017.51
15. Amano A. Disruption of epithelial barrier and impairment of cellular function by *Porphyromonas gingivalis*. *Front Biosci.* 2007;6:3965-3974. doi: 10.2741/2363
16. Nakagawa I, Amano A, Inaba H, Kawai S, Hama da S. Inhibitory effects of *Porphyromonas gingivalis* fimbriae on interactions between extracellular matrix proteins and cellular integrins. *Microbes Infect.* 2005;7(2):157-163. doi: 10.1016/j.micinf.2004.10.007
17. Fujita T, Ashikaga A, Shiba H, Uchida Y, Hirano C, Iwata T, et al. Regulation of IL-8 by Irsogladine maleate is involved in abolishment of *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*-induced reduction of gap-junctional intercellular communication. *Cytokine.* 2006;34(5-6):271-277. doi: 10.1016/j.cyto.2006.06.002
18. Noguchi T, Shiba H, Komatsuzawa H, Mizuno N, Uchida Y, Ouhara K, et al. Syntheses of prostaglandin E2 and E-cadherin and gene expression of β -defensin-2 by human gingival epithelial cells in response to *actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*. *Inflammation.* 2003;27(6):341-349. doi: 10.1023/B:IFLA.0000006702.27906.e9
19. Uchida Y, Shiba H, Komatsuzawa H, Hirano C, Ashikaga A, Fujita T, et al. Irsogladine maleate influences the response of gap junctional intercellular communication and IL-8 of human gingival epithelial cells following periodontopathogenic bacterial challenge. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 2005;333(2):502-507. doi: 10.1016/j.bbrc.2005.05.197
20. Damek-Poprawa M, Korostoff J, Gill R, Dirienzo JM. Cell junction remodeling in gingival tissue exposed to a microbial toxin. *J Dent Res.* 2013;92(6):518-523. doi: 10.1177/0022034513486807
21. Uitto VJ, Pan YM, Leung WK, Larjava H, Ellen RP, Finlay BB, et al. Cytopathic effects of *Treponema denticola* chymotrypsin-like proteinase on migrating and stratified epithelial cells. *Infect Immun.* 1995;63:3401-3410. doi: 10.1128/iai.63.9.3401-3410.1995
22. Galea I. The blood-brain barrier in systemic infection and inflammation. *Cell Mol Immunol.* 2021;18(11):2489-2501. doi: 10.1038/s41423-021-00757-x
23. Hijazi K, Lowe T, Meharg C, Berry SH, Foley J, Hold GL. Mucosal microbiome in patients with recurrent aphthous stomatitis. *J Dent Res.* 2015;94(3 Suppl):87S-94S. doi: 10.1177/0022034514565458
24. Pat Y, Yazici D, D'Avino P, Li M, Ardikli S, Ardikli O, et al. Recent advances in the epithelial barrier theory. *Int Immunol.* 2024;36(5):211-222. doi: 10.1093/intimm/dxae002
25. Kempuraj D, Thangavel R, Selvakumar GP, Zaheer S, Ahmed ME, Raikwar SP, et al. Brain and Peripheral Atypical Inflammatory Mediators Potentiate Neuroinflammation and Neurodegeneration. *Front Cell Neurosci.* 2017;11:216. doi: 10.3389/fncel.2017.00216
26. Vitkov L, Singh J, Schauer C, Minnich B, Krunic J, Oberthaler H, et al. Breaking the Gingival Barrier in Peri-odontitis. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2023;24(5):4544. doi: 10.3390/ijms24054544
27. Stehlikova Z, Tlaskal V, Galanova N, Roubalova R, Kreisinger J, Dvorak J., et al. Oral Microbiota Composition and Antimicrobial Antibody Response in Patients with Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis. *Microorganisms.* 2019;7(12):636. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms7120636
28. Su SC, Chang LC, Huang HD, Peng CY, Chuang CY, Chen YT, et al. Oral microbial dysbiosis and its performance in predicting oral cancer. *Carcinogenesis.* 2021;42(1):127-135. doi: 10.1093/carcin/bgaa062
29. Tsukita S, Furuse M. Overcoming barriers in the study of tight junction functions: from occludin to claudin. *Genes Cells.* 1998;3(9):569-73. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2443
30. Verma D, Garg PK, Dubey AK. Insights into the human oral microbiome. *Arch Microbiol.* 2018;200(4):525-540. doi: 10.1007/s00203-018-1505-3
31. Yang CY, Yeh YM, Yu HY, Chin CY, Hsu CW, Liu H, et al. Oral Microbiota Community Dynamics Associated With Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma Staging. *Front Microbiol.* 2018;9:862. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2018.00862
32. Yang J, Ran M, Li H, Lin Y, Ma K, Yang Y, et al. New insight into neurological degeneration: Inflammatory cytokines and blood-brain barrier. *Front Mol Neurosci.* 2022;15:1013933. doi: 10.3389/fnmol.2022.1013933
33. Yang SF, Huang HD, Fan WL, Jong YJ, Chen MK, Huang CN, et al. Compositional and functional variations of oral microbiota associated with the mutational changes in oral cancer. *Oral Oncol.* 2018;77:1-8. doi: 10.1016/j.oraloncology.2017.12.005
34. Moutsopoulos NM, Konkel JE. Tissue-Specific Immunity at the Oral Mucosal Barrier. *Trends Immunol. Пародонтология | Parodontologiya* 375 ОбзOp | Review 2018;39(4):276-287. doi: 10.1016/j.it.2017.08.005

35. Ronay V, Belibasakis GN, Schmidlin PR, Bostan ci N. Infected periodontal granulation tissue contains cells expressing embryonic stem cell markers. A pilot study. *Schweiz Monatsschr Zahnmed.* 2013;123(1):12-6. doi: 10.5167/uzh-77307
36. Dabija-Wolter G, Cimpan MR, Costea DE, Johan nessen AC, Sørnes S, Neppelberg E, et al. *Fusobacterium nucleatum* enters normal human oral fibroblasts in vi tro. *J Periodontol.* 2009;80(7):1174-83. doi: 10.1902/jop.2009.090051
37. Dutzan N, Konkel JE, Greenwell-Wild T, Moutso poulos NM. Characterization of the human immune cell network at the gingival barrier. *Mucosal Immunol.* 2016;9(5):1163-1172 doi: 10.1038/mi.2015.136
38. Tribble GD, Lamont RJ. Bacterial invasion of epi thelial cells and spreading in periodontal tissue. *Peri odontology* 2000. 2010;52(1):68-83. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0757.2009.00323
39. Akiyama SK, Olden K, Yamada KM. Fibronectin and integrins in invasion and metastasis. *Cancer Metas tasis Rev.* 1995 Sep;14(3):173-89. doi: 10.1007/BF00690290
40. Ye P, Yu H, Simonian M, Hunter N. Expression patterns of tight junction components induced by CD24 in an oral epi thelial cell-culture model correlated to affected periodontal tissues. *J Periodontal Res.* 2014;Apr;49(2):253-9. doi: 10.1111/jre.12102
41. Moonwiriyaakit A, Pathomthongtaweetchai N, Stein hagen PR, Chantawichitwong P, Satianrapapong W, Pong korpsakol P. Tight junctions: from molecules to gastroin testinal diseases. *Tissue Barriers.* 2023;11(2):2077620. doi: 10.1080/21688370.2022.2077620
42. Dabija-Wolter G, Bakken V, Cimpan MR, Johan nessen AC, Costea DE. In vitro reconstruction of human junctional and sulcular epithelium. *J Oral Pathol Med.* 2013;42(5):396-404. doi: 10.1111/jop.12005
43. Fujita T, Kishimoto A, Shiba H, Hayashida K, Kaji ya M, Uchida Y, , et al. Ir-sogladine maleate regulates neu trophil migration and E-cadherin expression in gingival epithelium stimulated by *Aggregatibacter actinomycetem comitans*. *Biochem Pharmacol.* 2010;79(10):1496–1505. doi: 10.1016/j.bcp.2010.01.017
44. Hartmann C, Schwietzer YA, Otani T, Furuse M, Ebnet K. Physiological functions of junctional adhesion molecules (JAMs) in tight junctions. *Biochim Biophys Acta Biomembr.* 2020;1862(9):183299. doi: 10.1016/j.bbamem.2020.183299
45. Otani T, Furuse M. Tight Junction Structure and Func tion Revisited. *Trends Cell Biol.* 2020 Oct;30(10):805-817. doi: 10.1016/j.tcb.2020.08.004.
- Erratum in: *Trends Cell Biol.* 2020;30(12):1014. doi: 10.1016/j.tcb.2020.10.001.
46. Kuo WT, Zuo L, Odenwald MA, Madha S, Singh G, Gurniak CB, et al. The Tight Junction Protein ZO-1 Is Dis pensable for Barrier Function but Critical for Effective Mu cosal Repair. *Gastroenterology.* 2021;161(6):1924-1939. doi: 10.1053/j.gastro.2021.08.047
47. González-Mariscal L, Betanzos A, Avila-Flores A. MAGUK proteins: structure and role in the tight junc tion. *Semin Cell Dev Biol.* 2000;11(4):315-24. doi: 10.1006/scdb.2000.0178
48. Paschoud S, Yu D, Pulimeno P, Jond L, Turner JR, Citi S. Cingulin and paracingulin show similar dynamic behaviour, but are recruited independently to junctions. *Mol Membr Biol.* 2011;28(2):123-35. doi: 10.3109/09687688.2010.538937
49. Belardi B, Hamkins-Indik T, Harris AR, Kim J, Xu K, Fletcher DA. A Weak Link with Actin Organizes Tight Junctions to Control Epithelial Permeability. *Dev Cell.* 2020;54(6):792-804.e7. doi: 10.1016/j.devcel.2020.07.022
50. Liévin-Le Moal V, Servin AL. The front line of en teric host defense against unwelcome intrusion of harm ful microorganisms: mucins, antimicrobial peptides, and microbiota. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2006;19(2):315-37. doi: 10.1128/CMR.19.2.315-337.2006
51. Patra AK, Amasheh S, Aschenbach JR. Modula tion of gastrointestinal barrier and nutrient transport function in farm animals by natural plant bioactive compounds – A comprehensive review. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.* 2019;59(20):3237-3266. doi: 10.1080/10408398.2018.1486284
52. Abe-Yutori M, Chikazawa T, Shibasaki K, Muraka mi S. Decreased expression of E-cadherin by *Porphy romonas gingivalis*-lipopolysaccharide attenuates epi thelial barrier function. *J Periodont Res.* 2017;52:42–50. doi: 10.1111/jre.12367
53. Yamada M, Takahashi N, Matsuda Y, Sato K, Yo koji M, Sulijaya B, et al. A bacterial metabolite ameliorates periodontal pathogen-induced gingival epithelial barrier disruption via GPR40 signaling. *Sci Rep.* 2018;8(1):9008. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-27408-y
54. Gimble, J. M., Katz, A. J., & Bunnell, B. A. (2007). Adipose-derived stem cells for regenerative medicine. *Circulation research*, 100(9), 1249–1260. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.RES.0000265074.83288.09>
55. Saliem, S., Bede, S., Cooper, P., Abdulkareem, A., Milward, M., & Abdullah, B. (2022). Pathogenesis of periodontitis – A potential role for epithelial-mesenchymal transition. *The Japanese*

Dental Science Review, 58, 268 - 278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdsr.2022.09.001>.

56. Saliem, S., Bede, S., Abdulkareem, A., Abdullah, B., Milward, M., & Cooper, P. (2022). Gingival tissue samples from periodontitis patients demonstrate epithelial-mesenchymal transition phenotype.. Journal of periodontal research. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jre.13086>.

57. Alanbari, B., Al-Taweel, F., Cooper, P., & Milward, M. (2024). Induction of Epithelial–Mesenchymal Transition in Periodontitis Rat Model. European Journal of Dentistry, 19, 428 - 437. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0044-1792011>.

58. Alanbari, B., Al-Taweel, F., Cooper, P., & Milward, M. (2024). Induction of Epithelial–

Mesenchymal Transition in Periodontitis Rat Model. European Journal of Dentistry, 19, 428 - 437. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0044-1792011>.

59. Abdulkareem, A., Shelton, R., Landini, G., Cooper, P., & Milward, M. (2018). Potential role of periodontal pathogens in compromising epithelial barrier function by inducing epithelial-mesenchymal transition. Journal of Periodontal Research, 53, 565–574. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jre.12546>.

60. Abdulkareem, A., Shelton, R., Landini, G., Cooper, P., & Milward, M. (2017). Periodontal pathogens promote epithelial-mesenchymal transition in oral squamous carcinoma cells in vitro. Cell Adhesion & Migration, 12, 127 - 137. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19336918.2017.1322253>.

For citation: Burkhonova Z.K., Samieva G.U. Potential role of epithelial-mesenchymal transition in the pathogenesis of periodontitis (literature review) // Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine. – 2025. – № 6(20). – P. 225–234. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17630104>